

Semicarbazones exhibit a broad band in the region $3150-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (H bonded OH) in their ir spectra. The disappearance of this band in the corresponding organotin complexes is indicative of deprotonation of both the protons of the semicarbazones and their subsequent participation in chelation. The band at 3440 cm^{-1} is assigned to NH_2 stretching mode which does not change on complexation, indicating its non-involvement in coordination. A strong band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in all the ligands due to azomethine group exhibits splitting on complexation, having one band located almost at the original position $1600 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to uncoordinated azomethine and the other shifted to lower frequency at $1585 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ arising from the coordinated $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ mode. The splitting of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ suggests that only one of the azomethine nitrogens is involved in coordination⁶. Several new bands at 570 ± 5 , 370 ± 5 , 270 ± 5 and at $235 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{O}^{\ominus}}$, $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{N}^{\ominus}}$, $\nu_{\text{asym Sn}-\text{Ph}}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym Sn}-\text{Ph}^{\oplus}}$, respectively.

The ^1H nmr spectra of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone and the complex were recorded in deuterated chloroform. In the spectrum of the complex, the peak due to OH protons disappears, which indicates deprotonation of the ligand. The signal for the azomethine proton in the salicylaldehyde semicarbazone at $\delta 8.50$ shifts towards higher field at $\delta 8.68$, indicating donation of lone-pair of electron to the central metal atom. Two groups of quadruplet and triplet observed at $\delta 7.67$ and 7.08 are attributed to the phenyl protons of ligand and Lewis acid, respectively. The structure of the complexes is tentatively assigned as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Structure of the complex: $\text{R}' = \text{Ph, Bu}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{H} = \text{R}_2$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_1 = 6,6\text{-Benzo}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$.

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References

1. H. J. FORSBERG, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1973, **10**, 195.
2. S. P. MITAL, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 199.

3. R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 602.
4. B. B. MAHAPATRA and S. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 526.
5. L. BHAL, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 951.
6. T. HARADA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1926, **4**, 266.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1956, p. 344.
8. R. SINGH, J. P. SRIVASTAVA and L. K. MISRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 805.
9. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and A. K. S. CHAUHAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 371.
10. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1967.
11. T. TANAKA, M. KOMURA, Y. KAWASAKI and R. OKAWARA, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1966, **1**, 484.

Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *N*-(8-Aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)-ethylenediamine and -propylenediamine Schiff Bases

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COUMARIN and its derivatives have been found to exhibit physiological activity and are also extensively used as analytical reagents^{1,2}. 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin has been found to exhibit anticoagulant and plant growth regulant property^{3,4}. The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterisation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with the Schiff bases *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)ethylenediamine (AHCE) and *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)propylenediamine (AHCP).

Experimental

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (AHC) was prepared by literature procedure⁵. The diamines (ethylenediamine and propylenediamine) were of B.D.H. quality. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The Schiff bases AHCE (m.p. 131.5°) and AHCP (m.p. 146°) were synthesised by refluxing AHC and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry ethanol medium for 30 min, and the yellow crystals separated on cooling were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

The metal chelates were prepared by refluxing the aqueous ethanolic solutions of the respective metal(II) chlorides (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) for 2-3 h on a water-bath. pH of the solution was adjusted to ~ 7 by dropwise addition of 10% sodium acetate solution. The precipitated metal

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} (298K) B.M.	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)
			N	OI	Metal			
[CoL(OH ₂) ₂ Cl]	Light pink	188	7.00 (7.19)	9.00 (9.11)	15.00 (15.12)	12.2	4.82	380 (389)
[NiL(OH ₂) ₂ Cl]	Green	184	7.00 (7.19)	8.98 (9.12)	14.88 (15.08)	14.0	3.22	380 (389)
[CuL(OH ₂) ₂ Cl]	Dark green	197d	6.97 (7.10)	8.86 (9.01)	15.95 (16.11)	13.0	1.91	382 (394)
[CoL'(OH ₂) ₂ Cl]	Light green	195d	6.72 (6.94)	8.62 (8.80)	14.45 (14.60)	11.0	4.81	391 (403)
[NiL'(OH ₂) ₂ Cl]	Green	190	6.70 (6.94)	8.61 (8.80)	14.40 (14.55)	12.5	3.21	390 (403)
[CuL'(OH ₂) ₂ Cl]	Green	182	6.68 (6.86)	8.61 (8.70)	15.41 (15.56)	9.4	1.91	393 (408)

* LH=C₁₄H₁₆O₂N₂(AHCE), L'H=C₁₄H₁₆O₂N₂(AHCP). ** Satisfactory C and H analyses.

complexes were filtered, washed repeatedly with ethanol followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and dried in vacuum.

The metal contents were determined⁶ by titration with 10⁻³ M EDTA. The ligands and complexes were analysed for C, H and N on a Thomas CH-Analyser-35 and Coleman N-Analyser-29 (C.D.R.I., Lucknow). Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a manually operated thermobalance with a heating rate of 5° per min. Differential thermal analysis was carried out by using Lead and Northrup DTA unit with a heating rate of 10° per min. Magnetic and spectral studies were made as reported earlier⁷. The molar conductance values of the complexes were measured in DMF (10⁻³ M) using a Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge with a cell having cell constant of 1.0 cm⁻¹. Molecular weights were determined by the camphor method. The analytical, magnetic moment and molar conductance data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All complexes behaved as non-electrolytes⁸ ($\Lambda_m < 14 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and molecular weight data (Table 1) showed their monomeric nature. The TG and DT analyses of all the complexes showed the presence of two molecules of coordinated water. The loss of water in all the complexes was a one step process. Only single endothermic peak at 184, 200 and 236° for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, respectively, were observed in DT analysis.

The bands appearing in the ir spectrum of the ligands at 1570s, 1100m and 560m cm⁻¹, which are characteristic of NH₂ (scissoring) +C=C (stretching), NH₂ (wagging) and NH₂ (rocking) modes, respectively⁹, suffered bathochromic shift (≈40 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes, clearly establishing the coordination of the amino group with metal ion⁹. A broad band, characteristic of ν_{OH} of coordinated water was observed in the region 3 500–3 200 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the complexes¹⁰. The presence of coordinated water was

further confirmed by the appearance of non-ligand band in the region¹¹ 835–845 cm⁻¹ assignable to rocking modes of water and also confirmed by TG and DT analysis. The absence of ν_{OH} (phenolic) (occurring at ~3 400 cm⁻¹ in the ligands) in the spectra of all the complexes suggested the cleavage of intramolecular hydrogen bonds¹² (OH) due to coordination of phenolate oxygen to the metal ions with deprotonation of the phenolic group. This was further confirmed by an upward shift¹³ of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) to the extent of 20–35 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (azomethine) band occurring in the region 1 620–1 600 cm⁻¹ in the ligands suffered a negative shift of 60–75 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating coordination of azomethine nitrogen^{14,15}. This was further supported by the appearance of $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (530–550 cm⁻¹) and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (440–475 cm⁻¹) bands in the spectra of all the complexes. The metal halogen (M–Cl) band were observed¹⁶ in the region 350–375 cm⁻¹.

The room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values (Table 1) of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were in the ranges expected for octahedral geometry¹⁷. The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibited bands around 25 650, 19 230, 17 860, 10 420 and 10 200 cm⁻¹, of which the first one was assigned to metal→ligand charge transfer because of its high intensity. The 19 230 cm⁻¹ band was assigned to the (ν_8) transition, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ for Co^{II} ion in octahedral environment^{18,19}. The 17 860, 10 420, and 10 200 cm⁻¹ bands were assigned to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(\nu_8)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^8A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{2g}$, respectively. The Ni^{II} complexes exhibited three typical bands at 26 330, 15 640 and 9 520 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions, ${}^8A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_8), ${}^8A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^8A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), respectively, in octahedral fields²⁰. Cu^{II} complexes showed a broad band (14 930–14 300 cm⁻¹) arising from the ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition²¹ in octahedral field. Based on above observations following structures could be proposed for these complexes where the Schiff base ligands AHCE and AHCP behaved as monoprotic (ONN) terdentate ligands.

$n = 0$ (AHCE), 1 (AHOP)
 $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$

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References

1. T. R. SEASHADRI and S. VARDARAJAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1952, **35**, 75.
2. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, R. L. GOEL and B. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 958.
3. R. B. ARORA and C. N. MATHAR, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1963, **20**, 29.
4. C. R. HANCOCK, H. B. BARLOW and H. J. LACEY, *J. Exptl. Bot.*, 1961, **12**, 401.
5. A. RUSSEL and J. R. FRYE, *Org. Synth.*, 1955, **3** 281.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1978, pp. 447, 462, 531.
7. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1089.
8. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
9. Y. INOMATO, T. INOMATO and T. MORIWAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 818.
10. R. L. DUTTA and R. K. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 185.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1970, pp. 159, 167, 214.
12. A. K. RANA and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1100.
13. N. S. BIRADAR, V. B. MOHALE and B. R. HAVINALE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 6.
14. J. OSASZAR and L. KISS, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1978, **78**, 17.
15. K. BURGER, "Coordination Chemistry: Experimental Method", Butterworths, London, 1973, p. 93.
16. N. SONODA and T. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 261.
17. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967.
18. A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 768.
19. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 87.
20. C. J. BALHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 256.
21. T. S. PIPER and R. L. BELFORD, *Mol. Phys.*, 1962, **5**, 169.

Complexes of Rhodium(III) and Palladium(II) with *N*-Vinylimidazole

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IN continuation of our studies on the transition metal complexes of benzimidazole and imidazole derivatives¹⁻⁶ we report herein the complexes of rhodium(III) and palladium(II) with *N*-vinylimidazole (NVIZ). The ligand coordinates as simple imidazole molecule leaving behind the vinyl group (CH=CH) uncoordinated.

Experimental

The reaction of NVIZ (0.004 mol) with an ethanolic solution of rhodium(III) chloride (0.001 mol in 50 ml) at reflux temperature gave cream yellow precipitate of $\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_3\text{Cl}_3$. The product on further refluxing for ~2 h on a steam-bath gave light yellow solution from which cream coloured crystalline precipitate of $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ separated on concentration and cooling. The perchlorate salt $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as cream white crystals on treating the concentrated reaction mixture with an aqueous solution of NaClO_4 .

The dichloro complex underwent substitution reaction with appropriate anions giving $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NO}_3$ or NCS) or $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$ or I). The diacido complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$ or I) were obtained on refluxing $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ with five-fold excess of KBr/KI in aqueous solution for 2 h. The complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NO}_3$ or NCS) were obtained on refluxing $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ with three-fold excess of $\text{NaNO}_3/\text{KNCS}$ in aqueous medium for 30 min. The complexes were isolated as crystalline products on concentrating and cooling the refluxates to small volume (yield 60–70%). The perchlorate derivative $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as cream coloured crystalline precipitate similar to $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Palladium(II) formed tetrakis complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ as well as diacido complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3$ or NCS). The complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ was prepared by refluxing an aqueous ethanolic solution of PdCl_2 (0.002 mol in 50 ml 90% ethanol) with five mole excess of the ligand on a steam-bath. The complex separated on concentration (pH 8). $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was readily formed when aqueous acidic solution of PdCl_2 (pH 2–3) was treated with hot ethanolic solution of ligand in stoichiometric proportion. The product was filtered after digesting it on a steam-bath. The dichloro complex underwent anion replacement reaction forming $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3$ or NCS) when refluxed in aqueous suspension with five-fold excess of potassium salt of an appropriate